

ONLINE FOOD ORDERING AND RECOMMENDER SYSTEM FOR BAZE
UNIVERSITY, ABUJA

Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirement

for the Award of

B.Sc.

In

Computer Science (Software Engineering)

By

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To

The Department of Computer Science

Baze University, Abuja

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DECLARATION

I, Muhammad Yakubu, hereby declare that this Thesis titled Online Food Ordering and Recommender System for Baze University, Abuja, which is submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the award of B.Sc. in Computer Science, majoring in Software Engineering to the Department of Computer Science, Baze University Abuja, Nigeria, is my original work. All sources and contributions used have been duly acknowledged.

Date:

Name of Student: Muhammad Yakubu

CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that the thesis titled Online Food Ordering and Recommender System for Baze University, Abuja, submitted by Muhammad Yakubu in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the B.Sc. degree in Computer Science, Majoring in Software Engineering, to the Department of Computer Science, Baze University Abuja, Nigeria is a record of the candidate's own work, conducted under my supervision. The content of this thesis is original and has not been submitted for the award of any other degree.

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APPROVAL

This project titled Online Food Ordering and Recommender System for Baze University, Abuja, by Muhammad Yakubu with Student ID: BU/22C/IT/7492 has been approved by the Department of Computer Science, Faculty of Computing and Applied Science, Baze University, Abuja, Nigeria as meeting the requirements for the B.Sc. degree in Computer Science, Majoring in Software Engineering.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate this project to the exalted lord, Allah SWT, on whose will and privilege I am witnessing this significant stage in my life. I also dedicate the project to my parents, Malam Yakubu Musa and Hajiya Hadiza, who have always been there for me and had faith in my abilities.

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In closing, I extend my sincere appreciation to the entire Computer Science department staff for the wealth of knowledge they have imparted in me.

ABSTRACT

Baze University Abuja has in the last couple of years witnessed unprecedented growth in terms of student population. This has led to a rise in the number of students who visit the university's cafeteria on a daily basis. Consequently, creating long queues around the cafeterias. This project titled Online Food Ordering and Recommender System for Baze University, Abuja seeks to address the challenges students and waiters face during the food ordering process. The core objective of the project is to create an efficient food ordering platform that offers students time-saving alternatives by reducing the need to visit the cafeteria physically and join lengthy queues to purchase food. The project always seeks to provide a recommendation system that takes into account past order history, customers' buying patterns, and individual preferences and offers personalized recommendations to them. The project adopted and followed agile methodology's guiding principles and iterative cycles that include requirement gathering, design, development, testing, deployment, and feedback. Finally, the successful implementation of the Online Food Ordering and Recommender System will address the challenges students face, reduce the workload on restaurant staff, and offer user satisfaction and accountability.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

DECLARATION	1
CERTIFICATION	1
APPROVAL	1
DEDICATION	1
ACKNOWLEDGMENT	1
ABSTRACT	1
LIST OF TABLES	4
LIST OF FIGURES	1
CHAPTER ONE	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Overview	1
1.2 Background and Motivation	1
1.2.1 Background	1
1.2.2 Motivation	2
1.3 Statement of the Problem	2
1.4 Aim and Objectives	3
1.4.1 Aim	3
1.4.2 Objectives	3
1.5 Significance of the Project	4
1.6 Project Risk Assessment	4
1.7 Scope	5
1.8 Project Organization	6
CHAPTER TWO	7
LITERATURE REVIEW	7
2.1 Introduction	7
2.2 Historical Overview	7
2.2.1 Types of Food Ordering System	8
2.2.2 Recommender System	9
2.3 Related Work	10
2.4 Summary	18
REQUIREMENT, ANALYSIS AND DESIGN	19
3.1 Overview	19
3.2 Proposed Model	19
3.3 Methodology	20
3.3.1 Method 1 (Interview)	21
3.3.2 Method 2 (Observation)	21
3.4 Tools and Techniques	22

3.5 Ethical Consideration	22
3.6 Requirement Analysis	22
3.7.1 Functional Requirement Specifications	23
3.7.2 Non-Functional Requirement Specifications	24
3.8 System Design	26
3.8.1 Application Architecture	27
3.8.2 Use Case	28
3.8.3 Data Design	29
3.8.4 Activity Diagrams	32
3.8.5 Control Flow Diagram	34
3.8.6 Entity Relationship Diagram (Erd)	35
3.8.7 User Interface Design	36
3.9 Summary	37
CHAPTER FOUR	38
IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING	38
4.1 Overview	38
4.2 Main Features	38
4.3 Implementation Problems	42
4.4 Overcoming Implementation Problems	42
4.5 Testing	43
4.5.1 Test Plans (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing, And System Testing)	43
4.5.2 Test Suite (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)	44
4.5.3 Test Traceability Matrix (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)	47
4.5.4 Test Report Summary (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)	48
4.5.5 Error Reports and Corrections	57
4.6 Use Guide	57
4.7 Summary	59
CHAPTER FIVE	60
DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS	60
5.1 Overview	60
5.2 Objective Assessment	60
5.3 Limitations and Challenges	60
5.4 Future Enhancements	61
5.5 Recommendations	62
5.6 Summary	63
References	64

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Summary of the Related Works	15
Table 2 Functional Requirement Specifications	23
Table 2.1 Non-Functional Requirement Specifications	25
Table 3.1 Data Dictionary for Customer Table	29
Table 3.2 Data Dictionary for Restaurant Table	30
Table 3.3 Data Dictionary for Menu Item Table	30
Table 3.4 Data Dictionary for Order Table	31
Table 4 Test Plans	43
Table 4.1 Test Suite	44
Table 4.2 Test Traceability Matrix	47
Table 4.3 Error Reports and Corrections	57

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Agile Model	20
Figure 2 Students' Queue	21
Figure 3.1 Application Architecture	27
Figure 3.2 Use Case Diagram	28
Figure 3.3 Order Process	32
Figure 3.4 Order Management	33
Figure 3.5 Control Flow Diagram	34
Figure 3.6 ERD	35
Figure 3.7 Wireframe	36
Figure 4 Sign Up page	39
Figure 4 Login page	39
Figure 4.2 Customer View page	40
Figure 4.3 Vendor View Page	42
Figure 5 Login with an Invalid Email	49
Figure 5.1 Login with valid credentials	50
Figure 5.2 Login with invalid credentials	51
Figure 5.3 Sign up with incorrect role	52

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

In the dynamic setting of the Baze University campus, where food is a daily necessity, students and staff throng en masse to the various cafeterias within the school to order food. Thus, they end up in long queues due to the high number of people, especially during rush hour.

This is why it has become necessary to come up with a solution tailored to address the challenges students and staff face in getting food from our cafeterias. The essence of this project lies in optimizing the whole dining experience by relieving the cafeteria staff of the stress that comes with attending to large crowds, saving students and staff valuable time that is wasted in long queues.

With technology as the driving force, this project addresses the issues of long waits for food, especially during peak hours. It seeks to offer a seamless and personalized food ordering experience, benefitting both the students and the cafeteria staff that work tirelessly to serve our campus community.

1.2 Background and Motivation

Like many other Universities, the Baze University campus also faces the challenges of crowded cafeterias and long waiting times at the food outlets. This is why in recent years, the landscape of food services has seen a massive evolution with online food ordering systems taking center stage.

1.2.1 Background

In the last few years, the University has witnessed a significant rise in the rate of student enrollment, resulting in more crowded cafeterias and lengthy queues. This situation has not only caused different sorts of inconveniences to the students' community but also stands as a potential threat to the quality of service being offered by the cafeteria staff, especially during rush hours.

1.2.2 Motivation

The motivation behind this research stems from the desire to mitigate the challenges of long queues faced by students and ensure that the quality of service offered by the cafeteria staff remains of the highest standard.

This project plans to leverage technology to overcome those challenges by providing a streamlined dining experience for our campus community that is user-centric and efficient. Thereby, benefiting not only the students but also the dedicated cafeteria staff who work tirelessly to cater to our campus community.

1.3 Statement of the Problem

The current food service system at the university has demonstrated an inability to ensure consistent quality of service. Students encounter frustration due to lengthy queues, which not only wastes their valuable time that could be better spent on academic pursuits but also places a heavy burden on cafeteria staff as they contend with a high influx of customers.

At present, the school utilizes meal-ordering booklets as a system for tracking students' cafeteria orders. While these booklets are useful for maintaining records of student orders, the manual nature of recording them leaves room for human errors, primarily because of the large number of daily orders handled by cafeteria staff. Additionally, there is the risk of students misplacing their booklets or using booklets that do not belong to them.

With technology in place, those issues can be alleviated as this project would offer students better options, including not having to carry physical booklets anytime they wish to purchase food from the cafeteria. Furthermore, the system will enhance record keeping by automatically generating records of every order and payment. Thus paving the way for a more transparent auditing process.

Additionally, the university's present system for providing food services lacks the capability of providing personalized food recommendations for customers. This project seeks to address that issue by providing tailored recommendations to customers, taking into account their individual preferences and past order history.

1.4 Aim and Objectives

1.4.1 Aim

This project aims to develop an online food ordering and recommender system for the university community.

1.4.2 Objectives

- ❖ **To Design an Efficient Food Ordering Platform:** To create a customer-centric food ordering platform that offers students time-saving alternatives by reducing the need to visit the cafeteria physically and join lengthy queues to purchase food.
- ❖ **To Provide Secure User Registration and Authentication:** To implement secure login and signup for both customers and vendors that allows only authenticated users to have access to the main parts of the system.
- ❖ **To Integrate Vendor Management:** To reduce the burden that cafeteria staff face to cater to customers and manage orders/menu items, leading to improved service quality, especially during peak hours.
- ❖ **To Implement a Recommender System:** To develop a recommendation algorithm that takes into account past order history, customers' buying patterns, and individual preferences to suggest similar items to customers.
- ❖ **To Conduct Series of Testing Techniques:** To conduct several testing techniques that include integration testing, unit testing, and system testing to ensure that the system functions correctly and meets the required standards.

1.5 Significance of the Project

In any institution of Baze University's magnitude, a project like this holds a profound significance. By introducing the online food ordering system, the workload faced by cafeteria staff during rush hours would be massively reduced and allow them to focus more on food preparation and delivering good quality service to customers. Likewise, from the student's end, the time that was otherwise wasted on long queues would be significantly reduced. Thus decongesting our cafeterias and allowing students to invest more time in their academic activities.

1.6 Project Risk Assessment

- **Data scarcity for personalized recommendations:** The menu items from the various cafeterias may be insufficient to offer more personalized recommendations to customers as they have limited options. To address this issue, the restaurants would have to look at expanding their menu and adding more items that are in demand.
- **User adoption and acceptance:** The restaurant staff and customers may initially resist adopting the system, preferring the traditional way of handling orders and expressing concerns about personalized recommendations.

To address this challenge, sessions would have to be conducted to raise awareness about the system's benefits and train users on how to use the system. Feedback from users would be collected through surveys to address areas in which users wish to see improvements.

1.7 Scope

This project will not consist of a mobile application. Nonetheless, it will be developed as a web application that works well in a variety of viewports, including desktop and mobile equivalents. The project's construction will allow it to house every food vendor on the university's campus. To construct a page, all they need to do is register their business with the system. A payment gateway will be added to the project to make the payment and checkout process more efficient. Likewise, a user may be able to access a wallet that they may directly fund and use to make payments. Furthermore, users can place orders by adding to carts and checking out from their respective carts. However, at the current moment, the users can only pick up their orders at the pickup points of each restaurant. Hence, no automated delivery service.

Additionally, the recommendation algorithms integrated into the system will offer tailored recommendations, that are content-based, to users based on their previous orders.

1.8 Project Organization

This section provides a clear roadmap of how every chapter will contribute to the development of this project. In Chapter 2, we review the existing works of other scholars who have worked on a similar project, thereby laying a solid foundation for the work. Chapter 3 talks about the requirements-gathering process, outlining how stakeholders were involved to make informed decisions that align with their needs. Chapter 3 will also reveal the design process and user interface. In Chapter 4, we will see practical implementation, including the choice of technology, integration and testing. Finally, in Chapter 5, we conclude and offer future recommendations based on our findings.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter will provide a thorough evaluation of related works done by scholars in this field. Through this study, we aim to integrate the wisdom of past endeavors which will pave the way for the innovative strides our project seeks to make in enhancing user experience and refining the restaurant workflow. Section 2.2 of this chapter is based on a historical overview of online food ordering and recommendation systems. 2.3 will review related works done in the past and finally, section 2.4 gives a summary of the entire chapter.

2.2 Historical Overview

In the past, before the advancements of technology, people placed orders in person at the respective seller's business place. Later on, with technological advancements, they moved to ordering using phone calls and websites. In 1922, a Chinese restaurant named "The Los Angeles Cafe Kin-Chu" made use of telephones to fulfill orders. Customers could call to place orders and the restaurant would deliver (Jackson, 2021). As years went by, websites were used for that purpose. According to Jackson (2021), one of the earliest web-based food delivery sites, Pizza Hut, debuted in 1994. In 1995, World Wide Waiter, the first online restaurant delivery service launched (Jackson, 2021). Since the early 2000s, there has been an incredible evolution in the online food ordering sector. Food delivery became more popular as smartphones became popular around the world. People could order food and get it delivered to their doorsteps. China's online food ordering and delivery market rose from 0.15 billion CNY in 2010 to 44.24 billion CNY in 2015 (He et al., 2019). This serves as even more confirmation that the online food ordering market has grown significantly over the years. Ramli et al., (2021) opined that the most critical targeted audience for most businesses in the food service industry is the millennials (people under 30) and using an online ordering system is the easiest way to reach them. During the Covid-19 outbreak, even the most traditional customers were forced to explore online purchasing and ordering services. As a result, many restaurant businesses and food services migrated to using online services (Ramli et al., 2021).

In Nigeria, the online food ordering sector has witnessed a tremendous amount of growth over the years, especially with the rise of internet access across the country. Since the launch of Jumia Food in the early 2010s, many other similar platforms, local and international brands, have entered the online food ordering sector. A report predicts the online food delivery market in Nigeria to reach a staggering \$2.83 billion in 2024 (TagiAfrica, 2024). Established international companies like Glovo and Bolt Food have simplified food ordering in the country by providing seamless ordering experiences to customers. Another key player in the sector is Chowdeck, a startup founded in 2021 by a group of three Nigerians with the aim of providing online food ordering and delivery services to Nigerians. Since its inception, Chowdeck has grown from strength to strength. The company now boasts an average delivery time of 30 minutes, making it one of the fastest food delivery services in Africa (TagiAfrica, 2024).

2.2.1 Types of Food Ordering System

A food ordering system is a technological solution for the food service industry that makes ordering easy for both customers and businesses (FHA-HoReCa, 2024). According to FHA-HoReCa, 2024, the types of food ordering systems include:

- ❖ **Online Food Ordering Platforms:** These are web-based platforms that enable customers to view menus, place orders and make payments.
- ❖ **Mobile Ordering Apps:** These are mobile applications that allow customers to order food using smartphones or tablets.
- ❖ **Integrated POS Systems:** They are point-of-sale systems that are designed with food ordering capabilities that handle both in-house and online orders.
- ❖ **Voice-Activated Ordering:** These are systems that allow customers to make orders using voice commands. They are majorly AI-driven.

- ❖ **Social Media Ordering:** They are features built into social media platforms that allow users to place orders within the apps.

2.2.2 Recommender System

Moving to recommender systems, on the other hand, recommender systems aim to provide users with a list of recommendations of items that a service offers (Hug, 2020). According to Qomariyah (2020), the concept of recommender system (RS) was first implemented in 1979 through a program called Grundy, a computer-based librarian that recommended books to read to the user. The 1990s kick-started the era of modern-day recommender systems. With advancements in the World Wide Web, major tech companies like Amazon, Netflix, and YouTube adopted recommender systems in their various products to improve the overall user experience and generate suggestions that are specific to the interests of each user.

Amazon.com launched item-based collaborative filtering in 1998, enabling recommendations at a previously unseen scale for millions of customers and a catalog of millions of items (Smith & Linden, 2017). Furthermore, according to Smith & Linden (2017), Amazon.com has been creating a unique shopping experience for each customer. Every person who visits to amazon.com sees it differently because it's individually personalized based on their interests.

Similarly, Netflix uses recommender systems to offer viewers personalized movie recommendations based on their preferences. In 2006, Netflix launched the "Netflix Prize", a competition that offered a 1 million US dollar prize to the winner that built the best movie recommender system for them (Qomariyah, 2020).

As already pointed out, Recommender systems have been developed using AI and ML to improve user experience on various software systems in different fields over the years. According to Inference Labs (2021), based on an assessment of countless data elements, AI and ML offer current industry insights, forecasts, and emerging food trends. Because of this, food delivery companies are capable of adjusting to new flavors and ingredients that are in demand by their customers.

2.3 Related Work

Researchers have put a lot of work into the advancement of online food ordering systems. Every effort they have put in has served as a stepping stone and contributed immensely to the enhancement of digital food services across the globe.

Adegoke(2021) developed a cafeteria food ordering system in which customers can order meals online using the application by registering online, reading the e-menu card, and selecting the item from the e-menu card. The application eliminates the need for a waiter or decreases the waiter's duty at his university. However, the system could only accommodate a single vendor as it was not designed for others to come and register. Consequently, there is still an opportunity for advancements to improve the user experience.

Dana et al. (2021), in a study, found the use of online ordering services is most prevalent among younger individuals as well as those with higher education levels and income. This makes the university campus a great fit for such projects. According to Gupta (2019), when customers pick up their smartphones to use your online ordering platform, they do it at their convenience and when such platforms are built the right way, they can help cultivate customer loyalty and enhance profitability. This is totally in line with Kanishka (2014), who is of the view that marketers need to develop an insightful understanding of consumer behaviour when purchasing products online as the information helps them to better meet customer's requirements. By doing so, companies will build strong brand loyalty and increase customer satisfaction.

According to Frederick & Bhat (2021), Customers' encounters with the company's website, features, and product quality have a significant impact on the ordering process when they order food online. Certainly, to address the impact of customers' encounters with the company's website, features, and product quality on the online ordering process, businesses can focus on creating a user-centric digital environment. This includes designing an intuitive and visually appealing website interface with clear navigation, high-quality images, and customization options.

Similarly, a study by Zulkarnain et al. (2015), asserts that system quality, information quality, and service quality are critical to satisfying customers and increasing their loyalty toward online food ordering operators. Kanishka (2014), in a study, found some challenges faced by customers while ordering food electronically. 27 percent of the customers admit

that while ordering online food the site is slow followed by 26 percent who say the delivery time is more whereas 24 percent of the site is not opening and the least is 19 percent who say that the Service follow-up is poor. To address these challenges system quality, information quality and service quality have to be put into consideration.

The development of the online food ordering sector will now be determined by innovation and technology. Technology can be the potential tool to give food providers significant cost and efficiency gains as well as the ultimate goal of making customers happy (Thamaraiselvan et al., 2019).

As was mentioned in the preceding section, prominent tech businesses like Amazon and Netflix have since adopted recommender systems to enhance user experience. They mostly use data such as ratings, watch history and location information to make those recommendations. When you view something on Netflix, a variety of data is collected by the system, which is then used by recommendation algorithms to update recommendations on your profile home page the following day (Mangla, 2023).

Recommender systems allow the quick and automated customization and personalization of e-commerce sites. By bundling closely related items together, they help in the up-selling of extra products and allow the sites to generate more sales by tailoring the needs of visitors (Madni et al., 2014). According to Jansen et al. (2024), the simplest way to generate recommendations is a non-personalized recommender system that suggests the same products to each user, such as the most popular item in the store and does not consider individual preferences.

One aspect that provides a problem for building food recommenders is the data (Anderson, 2018). To incorporate recommender systems into food ordering systems, nevertheless, there is a need for data to be collected from users, as seen from Netflix. This data can be in the form of ratings or past order history of the user. It could also be from users that have similar purchasing patterns.

The recommender systems can be divided into three main branches according to different strategies – collaborative filtering (CF), content-based, and a combination of both (Zhang et al., 2014). Among the recommendation techniques proposed in literature are content-based filtering and collaborative filtering (Iaquinta et al., 2008). Systems that use the

content-based filtering (CBF) technique examine a collection of documents, often textual summaries of the things that a single user has previously rated, and create a model or profile of that person's interests based on the characteristics of the items that user has previously rated (Iaquinta et al., 2008). Content-based filtering does not rely on data from other users or their behavior information. The method is capable of providing relevant recommendations even to new users (Kosim & Reza, 2023). On the other hand, in collaborative filtering (CF), recommendation for each active user is received by comparing with the preferences of other users who have rated the product in similar way to the active user (Thorat et al., 2015). The two widely used techniques have their advantages and limitations.

According to Cheng et al. (2014) one advantage of content-based filtering is user independence as the technique mainly depends on ratings provided by the users to learn about their preferences. Moreover, the content-based filtering technique does not suffer from a cold start. On the other hand, the collaborative filtering technique will have that issue as only items rated by a multiple number of users will be recommended. Cheng et al. (2014), also stated that in the absence of user feedback, the collaborative filtering technique will have difficulty in finding similar users.

Peretz et al. (2008), in a study revealed that the significance of an item provided by a system to a user can be determined by either implicit or explicit user feedback. The user feedback enables the system to regularly update users' profiles according to what they like and dislike. The implicit feedback is more difficult to implement and gotten by observing the user's behavior and interactions.

Cheng et al. (2014), developed an application that keeps track of user interactions with the system. The application offers suggestions to those without idea what to cook. In order to recommend a recipe that the user may like, the weight of each item and category is collected by keeping track of how the number of times a particular page is visited and the number of times an item is viewed. The application offers solutions to the user's problems however, the amount of information about the user's activities and interactions with the system collected at different times poses a serious privacy concern.

Today most e-commerce sites and applications are likely to have some sort of recommendation engine powering their user experience (Amatriain & Basilico, 2015). Social media platforms like Instagram, Facebook, etc also utilize recommender systems to enhance user experience. X, formerly Twitter, for example, introduced their “Who to Follow recommendation” algorithm to recommend new social connections (Amatriain & Basilico, 2015). Thus, solidifying the significance of the Recommender Systems (RS) in user retention and user experience.

According to Teppan & Zanker (2015), recommender systems tend to have decision biases, especially on result and comparison pages. And, to help users make more objective decisions during their interaction with recommendation systems, it is essential to equip them with tools that allow the identification and neutralization of misleading biases.

As mentioned earlier, unlike collaborative filtering that focuses on user interests, content-based filtering is influenced by factors such as the item’s description, title, ingredients, or genre when the item is a movie. One effective way of implementing the CBF approach is using Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF) algorithm and cosine similarity. TF-IDF calculates the significance of a word in a document. The TF-IDF value of a word indicates its level of characterization within that document and a higher value signifies how important the word is (Hiro & Toto, 2023). Whereas, according to Hiro & Toto (2023), Cosine similarity is used to assess the similarity between target data and a given set of data.

It evaluates how similar two documents are by considering their differences in size and calculates the cosine angle between the two vectors in a multidimensional space. Consequently, recommendations are then computed based on the similarities between the items available and the ones associated with specific users.

Table 1 Summary of the Related Works

Related Work	Method/Approach	Key Findings	Weaknesses
Adegoke (2021)	Developed an online an online cafeteria food ordering system	-The system simplified the food ordering process -It reduced reliance on waiters	-It did not provide the opportunity to accommodate or register multiple vendors.
Dana et al. (2021)	Studied the demographics of online food ordering platform users	-Revealed the information about the demographics	-It did not address user experience
Gupta (2019)	Studied the impact of online food ordering platform on businesses	-Showed the benefits of such platforms to restaurants	-It did not address recommendation systems
Kanishka (2014)	Identified challenges faced by users	-Highlighted key areas that users have challenges	-It focused majorly on challenges and not the solutions to the challenges
Frederick & Bhat (2021)	Analyzed website features for better user experience	-Highlighted the of aesthetics and user centric approach	-It did not offer a detailed implementation guide
Zulkarnain et al. (2015)	Focused on technical quality and customer retention strategies	-Identified and analyzed system, information, and	-It did not address emerging technologies

		service quality as essential for customer loyalty	
Thamaraiselvan et al. (2019)	Examined the role of technology in Indian food delivery app	-Provided insights into the impacts of technology on the market	-It focused on only the Indian market
Mangla (2023)	Focused on Netflix's use of data in making recommendations	-Showed the significance of in making quality recommendations	-Focused mainly on entertainment platforms
Jansen et al. (2024)	Investigated recommendation systems in online grocery shopping	-Identified non-personalized recommendations as a simple and easy to implement approach for new users	-Non-personalized recommendations may not always be what the user wants
Anderson (2018)	Surveyed the use of recommender systems in food services	-Showed the importance of data collection in making effective recommendations	-It did not offer practical data collection strategies
Zhang et al. (2014)	Focused on different recommendation techniques	-Compared the different techniques	-It did not address integration challenges

Iaquinta et al. (2008), Kosim & Reza (2023)	Proposed Content-based filtering for making personalized recommendations	-Effective for new users with zero interaction data with the system	-Can limit the recommendations as it only focuses on a single user
Thorat et al. (2015)	Looked at Collaborative filtering based on user similarities	-It offers diverse recommendations	-It is not suitable for new users
Amatriain & Basilico (2015)	Looked at Netflix's recommender system	-Provided insights into large scale deployments of the systems	-It focused mainly on entertainment platforms and social media
Teppan & Zanker (2015)	Analyzed recommender systems and identified issues like bias	-Gave insights into recommendation bias	-It did not focus on overall system design

2.4 Summary

In summary, the literature reviewed in this chapter has provided a comprehensive analysis of the historical overview of online food ordering and recommender systems as seen in section 2.2. Moreso, section 2.3 took us through related works as we explored existing strategies and potential gaps to address in our project. Looking forward, Chapter 3 will delve into crucial phases of requirement, analysis and design.

CHAPTER THREE

REQUIREMENT, ANALYSIS AND DESIGN

3.1 Overview

This chapter contains the requirements-gathering process of this project. It will reveal the proposed model, methodology, and the application's architecture. The chapter will also outline the system design and functional and non-functional requirements.

3.2 Proposed Model

The proposed model for this application is the Agile model also known as plan-driven development. We intend to adopt the Agile model because of its iterative approach to software development. It is divided into phases that include requirement gathering, analysis, designing the requirements, development/iteration, testing, deployment, and feedback. This iterative technique aligns with the project's complexity as it enables careful planning, reducing risks, and delivering a high-quality final product that satisfies the needs of our consumers and stakeholders. For a graphic representation of the Agile model, see Figure 1.

Figure 1 Agile Model (JavaTPoint)

3.3 Methodology

Agile methodology has been selected as the guiding framework to deliver this project. The Agile methodology is an iterative approach to software development that offers a dynamic way to respond to changing requirements. It is based on guiding principles that include Incremental delivery, Customer involvement, Maintaining simplicity, Embracing change, and People not process.

A project is typically broken up into manageable chunks using the agile technique, which includes planning, design, implementation, testing, and maintenance. Agile demands continuous client input. As a result, the project continues to meet the expectations of the user since the project's delivery revolves around the user's feedback.

3.3.1 Method 1 (Interview)

An Interview was conducted, featuring both students and cafeteria staff to get their opinion regarding the proposed online food ordering and recommender system. Both parties expressed their excitement at the suggestion and also provided their thoughts on how they believe the system should be implemented.

3.3.2 Method 2 (Observation)

Over the course of this process, a covert observation was carried out. The covert technique involved the researcher being physically present at the cafeterias to perform the normal food ordering process. The need for an Online food ordering system at the university campus became clearer as the researcher had to go through long queues on most occasions. Furthermore, it became apparent that the restaurant staff were overwhelmed by the high number of people there. Hence, they could not deliver service of the highest quality. Figure 3 depicts the cafeterias' influx of customers during peak hours.

Figure 2 Students' Queue

3.4 Tools and Techniques

This section outlines the tools and techniques that are essential to the successful delivery of this project. They are as follows:

- I. **Documentation tools:** Google Docs, MS Word and Notepad have been chosen as the tools to facilitate the documentation of this project.
- II. **Prototyping and Design Tools:** The prototyping and design tools selected for this project are: draw.io, workbench and StarUML.
- III. **Text Editor:** Visual Studio code and Jupyter Notebook.
- IV. **Version Control System:** For the version control of this system, Git Hub has been selected as the designated platform to use.
- V. **Programming Languages and Frameworks:** Python, Django Rest Framework, JavaScript, and React Js.

3.5 Ethical Consideration

The ethical considerations majorly lie in user privacy and data protection, transparency and accountability. User data and information will be treated with utmost care by using firm encryption techniques to ensure that their information is safeguarded. There will be transparency and accountability as the user will be well informed on how the recommendations systems work to provide suggestions to them.

3.6 Requirement Analysis

The conducted interview and observation serve as building blocks for the requirement analysis. From the user's perspective, we were able to pinpoint an intuitive and user-friendly interface that is mobile responsive as a crucial requirement. The user requirements also streamlined order tracking, delivery options and personalized recommendations. Likewise, the requirements identified based on the restaurant staff's perspective included a user-friendly dashboard that helps in managing menu items and their availability, viewing orders, payment and delivery status. Additionally, our observation showed that the system's efficiency and scalability when the user base increases must be given a substantial amount of priority to manage a possibly large number of people.

3.7 Requirement Specifications

This section will specify the functional and non-functional requirements of the system. On the grounds of this, we establish a clear and concise, yet robust framework upon which the system will be developed.

3.7.1 Functional Requirement Specifications

Table 2 Functional Requirement Specifications

Req. No	Description	Type
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R-001	The customer shall be able to register and log in.	Functional
R-002	Customers shall be able to view menu items.	Functional
R-003	The customer shall be able to make an order.	Functional
R-004	The customer shall be able to view the order history.	Functional
R-005	Customers shall be able to able to rate and review individual dishes.	Functional
R-006	Admin shall have access to a dashboard where he/she can view transaction records and set menu item's price.	Functional
R-007	Restaurant staff shall have access to a dashboard to manage their menu, update item availability and view incoming orders.	Functional
R-008	The recommendation engine shall provide personalised	Functional

	recommendations based on user preferences and past order history.	
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3.7.2 Non-Functional Requirement Specifications

Table 2.1 Non-Functional Requirement Specifications

Req. No	Description	Type
R-001	The system shall ensure user privacy and data security.	Security
R-002	The system shall be available 24/7.	Availability
R-003	The system shall be mobile-responsive.	Usability
R-004	The system shall have a good-looking and easy-to-use user interface.	Usability
R-005	The system shall handle a large number of users without performance degradation.	Performance
R-006	The system shall adhere to the provided guidelines	Compliance

	regarding user data protection.	
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3.8 System Design

This section provides a detailed summary of the major components that make up the online food ordering and recommender system. They are as follows:

- I. REGISTRATION / SIGNUP: Here, a new user of the system gets registered. The registration options are either as a customer or as a restaurant. For both scenarios, different types of data would be collected during the registration process.
- II. LOGIN: On the log-in page, existing users of the system, who have registered will put in their login details to access the system's home page.
- III. RESTAURANT MANAGEMENT: For each restaurant, there will be an admin who is responsible for overseeing the restaurant's operations. The admin would be responsible for adding a restaurant staff that would manage the restaurant's menu and process orders.
- IV. RECOMMENDATION ENGINE: Here, Machine learning will be utilized to generate personalized recommendations to the customers based on their feedback and past orders.
- V. FEEDBACK / RATINGS: Customers will be able to rate menu items and offer input, which will enable the recommendation engine to give them tailored recommendations.
- VI. PAYMENT: In the payment section third-party payment gateway will be used. The customer may decide to fund their personal wallet on the system or pay using cards, cash or bank transfer.
- VII. HOME: The home page will contain a list of available restaurants that the users can buy from. By clicking on the restaurant's profile, a customer will have the chance to view their menu items, select the an and place orders.

3.8.1 Application Architecture

This section contains the application's architecture. It will reveal how the client side communicates with the server side. Figure 4 illustrates how data is transferred between the front-end and the back-end.

Figure 3.1 Application Architecture

3.8.2 Use Case

The use case will demonstrate the functions of every actor in the system. They include the customer, restaurant admin and restaurant staff.

Figure 3.2 Use Case Diagram

Actors: Customer and Vendor.

Customer: The customer can sign up/log in, place an order, pay and rate menu items.

Vendor: Sign up as a restaurant, set menu price, add/remove menu items and approve restaurant staff.

3.8.3 Data Design

The following tables provide details on some of the entities that will be stored in the database.

Table 3.1 Data Dictionary for Customer Table

Attribute Name	Type	Required	PK / FK
Customer_id	Integer	Yes	PK
First_name	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Last_name	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Email	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Phone	Integer	Yes	–
Password	Varchar(45)	Yes	–

Table 3.2 Data Dictionary for Restaurant Table

Attribute Name	Type	Required	PK / FK
Restaurant_id	Integer	Yes	PK
Name	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Description	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Address	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Contact_number	Integer	Yes	–

Logo	Blob	Yes	–
Registration_date	Date	Yes	–
Password	Varchar(45)	Yes	–

Table 3.3 Data Dictionary for Menu Item Table

Attribute Name	Type	Required	PK / FK
Item_id	Integer	Yes	PK
Restaurant_id	Integer	Yes	Fk
Name	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Description	Varchar(45)	Yes	–
Price	Integer	Yes	–
Availability_status	Enum	Yes	–
Category	Enum	Yes	–
Item_image	Blob	Yes	–

Table 3.4 Data Dictionary for Order Table

Attribute Name	Type	Required	PK / FK
Order_id	Integer	Yes	PK
Restaurant_id	Integer	Yes	Fk
Customer_id	Integer	Yes	Fk
Total_amount	Integer	Yes	–
Order_status	Enum	Yes	–
Item_id	Integer	Yes	Fk
Order_date	Date	Yes	–

3.8.4 Activity Diagrams

Figure 3.3 presents a diagrammatic representation of the order process from the customer's perspective.

Figure 3.3 Order Process

Figure 3.4 displays how an order is being handled by the restaurant staff.

Figure 3.4 Order Management

3.8.5 Control Flow Diagram

Figure 3.5 Control Flow Diagram

3.8.6 Entity Relationship Diagram (Erd)

Figure 3.6 ERD

3.8.7 User Interface Design

We'll see a wireframe in this section that will act as the basic design guide for the online meal ordering and recommendation system. It describes the structure and arrangement of the content from the customer's perspective.

Figure 3.7 Wireframe

3.9 Summary

In this chapter, we explored the stages of requirement gathering, analysis, and design. Section 3.1 provided an overview of the chapter's content. In sections 3.2 and 3.2 we discussed our proposed model and chosen methodology, followed by a discussion on the necessary tools and techniques for project implementation. We outlined both functional and non-functional requirements in this chapter. Additionally, section 3.8 presented our system's architecture, use case scenarios, Entity-Relationship Diagram (ERD), and user interface wireframe. The following chapter will leverage Chapter 3, explaining how we implement and test the various components that form our system.

CHAPTER FOUR

IMPLEMENTATION AND TESTING

4.1 Overview

This chapter contains the project's implementation and testing processes. It will provide information about the main features of the system, the problems encountered during implementation and how they were overcome. The chapter will also outline the testing processes, including test plans and results. The chapter will conclude by providing a detailed use guide of the system and a summary of the overall implementation and testing outcomes.

4.2 Main Features

The main features of this system include:

AUTHENTICATION: This feature is further divided into signup and login. A new user must sign up by filling out a signup form. The form contains a role field, a drop-down with two options; customer and vendor. By selecting either of the two options, the user's account type is determined. Subsequently, by submitting the form, the information is stored in the database and an account is created for the user. The login section is for users who have created an account. They log into the system with the credentials they used to sign up.

A screenshot of a "Sign Up" form. The form includes fields for Email (johndoe@email.com), Account Type (Select Role), Password (Enter password), and Confirm Password (Confirm password). A Submit button is at the bottom, and a link for "Already have an account? Login" is at the bottom right.

Figure 4 Sign Up page

Figure 4.1 Login Page

CUSTOMER VIEW PAGE: The customer view page is a crucial feature of the system that acts as the main page for the customers. It consists of a list of vendors registered on the system's database including links to the respective vendors' page. Some of the key elements of the customer view page include:

- Link to Cart page
- Link to the Order history page
- A comprehensive list of recommendations for the customer
- Logout Button
- A link to the Customer's profile page

Figure 4.2 Customer View page

VENDOR VIEW PAGE: Similar to the customer view page, this page serves as the central page for the vendors where they view and manage their respective businesses. It is designed as a dashboard where a vendor can view pending orders, successful orders, canceled orders and their earnings of the month. It also consists of a bar chart for visualization and analytics of the week's top-selling category between food, drinks, or snacks. The page also consists of links to key features and pages such as:

- **Vendor Profile Page:** The page consists of information about the vendor that can be viewed by the customer. The vendor can also modify their details on the page.

- **Menu Items Page:** This page allows the vendors to add, modify, or remove menu items from the list of items that they sell. Each vendor can also see a list of the items they have available in stock.
- **Order Page:** The order page consists of a list of all orders made to the vendor's store. Through this page, the vendor can update the order status to either canceled or successful.
- **Log Out:** This feature allows the vendor to end a browsing session. For the vendors to regain access back into the system, they have to log in using their credentials.

Figure 4.3 Vendor View Page

Other key features and functionalities of the system include: adding to the cart, removing items from the cart, updating the user profile, placing orders, viewing vendors, and viewing recommendations.

4.3 Implementation Problems

During the implementation phase of this project, the major challenges encountered were the integration of Tailwind CSS (a CSS framework) and Shadcn UI (a UI component library) into the project. The main issues were not setting up the tailwind config file properly, and not creating a jsonconfig.json file for the Shacn UI. These significantly slowed down the development process as time that was initially allocated for other tasks was used to resolve the issues.

4.4 Overcoming Implementation Problems

To address the issues, I followed the official documentation of both Tailwind CSS and Shadcn UI, I also checked Stackoverflow to gain insights into how developers who have encountered similar problems before were able to resolve them. By following the sources mentioned above, especially the official channels, I learned how to properly configure Tailwind CSS to work with react.js and set up Shadcn UI to work with JavaScript rather than its default Typescript.

4.5 Testing

Different kinds of testing strategies and techniques such as unit testing have been employed to ensure the system's functionality, performance, and usability. The use of Postman, an API testing tool, to test my API endpoints was crucial for debugging the system as it allowed for easy simulation of HTTP requests to ensure the backend services were functioning correctly. It helped in verifying the HTTP status codes and the accuracy of the returned responses.

4.5.1 Test Plans (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing, And System Testing)

Table 4 Test plans

Test Plan ID	Test Type	Test Objective	Test Tools
TP-01	Unit Testing	Ensure that each individual module works correctly.	Postman

TP-02	Integration Testing	Ensure that different parts of the system, especially the Frontend and Back-End services work correctly together after integration; making sure that data is accurately communicated between them.	Postman, Chrome Dev Tools
TP-03	System Testing	Ensuring the overall functionality and performance of the system, making sure that all functional and non functional requirements are met.	Postman, Chrome Dev Tools

4.5.2 Test Suite (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)

Table 4.1 Test Suite

Test Suite ID	Test Type	Test Description	Test Steps	Expected Outcome
TS-01	Unit Testing	Test user sign-up/registration.	1-Navigate to the signup page 2- Fill out the form with both valid and invalid details (eg signing up with an already registered email)	The sign-up should be successful for valid data and should fail in a case where invalid data is submitted.

			3-Submit	
TS-02	Unit Testing	Test user login	1- Navigate to the login page 2-Log in with both valid and invalid credentials 3- Submit	Successful log-in for valid credentials, log-in should fail given invalid credentials
TS-03	Unit Testing	Test add to cart functionality	1- Login as a customer 2-Select a particular vendor 3-Pick an item from the vendor and click on add to cart	The item should be added to the customer's cart
TS-04	Integration Testing	Test order placing	1- Add items to the cart 2- Place order	The order should be placed Details of the order should be reflected on the order history page and the vendor's dashboard
TS-05	Integration Testing	Test viewing order history	1- Login as a customer 2-Navigate to order	The page should contain previous orders of the

			history page	customer
TS-06	Integration Testing	Test recommendations	1- Place order(s)	The recommendations should be personalized based on the customer's order history
TS-07	System Testing	Test accessing protected routes	1- Attempt accessing protected routes such as the customer view page, and vendor dashboard without logging in	Access should be denied and the user redirected back to the login page
TS-08	System Testing	Test viewing registered vendors from customer view	1- Login as a customer 2-View vendors' list	A list of registered vendors should be displayed with their details
TS-09	System Testing	Test viewing, deleting, and updating menu items from the vendor side	1- Login as a vendor 2-Navigate to the menu items' page 3-view and modify item	Vendors should be able to make changes to an item Changes made on any item should be reflected on the customers' side

TS-10	System Testing	Test modifying order status	1- Login as a vendor 2-Navigate to the order page 3-view and modify order status	Vendors should be able to successfully change the status of an order Changes made should be reflected on the customers' side
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4.5.3 Test Traceability Matrix (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)

Table 4.2 Test Traceability Matrix

Test Case ID	Test Description	Status
TC-01	Sign up with valid data	Pass
TC-02	Reject sign up with already registered email	Pass
TC-03	Login with valid credentials	Pass
TC-04	Reject Login with unregistered/invalid credentials	Pass
TC-05	Clicking add to cart button should add the item to cart	Pass
TC-06	Place order button should send order to vendor	Pass

TC-07	View placed orders in order history page	Pass
TC-08	Display list of registered vendors on customer view page	Pass
TC-09	Deny access to protected routes by unauthenticated users	Pass
TC-10	Add, edit and delete menu items by vendor	Pass
TC-11	View, modify order status by vendor	Pass
TC-12	View personalized recommendations on customers' side	Pass

4.5.4 Test Report Summary (For Unit Testing, Integration Testing And System Testing)

During the testing process, most of the test cases performed as expected. User signup with an invalid email was rejected. Similarly, logging in with invalid credentials was denied. See the following images for details:

Figure 5 Login with an Invalid Email

Figure 5.2 Login with invalid credentials

Figure 5.3 Sign up with incorrect role

The image shows a login form with the following elements:

- Title:** Login
- Email Label:** Email
- Email Input:** A text box containing the email address "erer.122@email.". The input box has a thin black border.
- Error Message:** "Invalid email" displayed in red text below the email input.
- Password Label:** Password
- Password Input:** A text box containing seven dots, representing a masked password.
- Login Button:** A dark blue button with the text "Login" in white.
- Links:** "Forgot password?" and "Signup" located below the login button.

Figure 5.4 Email format validation

Figure 5.5 Login with invalid credentials

Sign Up

Email

Account Type

This is your account type

Password

Confirm Password

Submit

Already have an account

⚠ passwords do not match

Figure 5.6 Sign up with different passwords

Figure 5.7 Sign up with already registered email

4.5.5 Error Reports and Corrections

Table 4.3 Error Reports and Corrections

Error ID	Description	Correction	Status
ER-01	Missing “.as_view()” method in user/urls.py file while using classed based view	Adding the method to every view called in the urls.py file	Fixed

4.6 Use Guide

Step 1:

User registration/Signup

Step 2:

Create a user profile based on the registered account type

Step 3:

Log in to the designated account type

Step 4:

For customers, a list of registered vendors will be displayed on the customer view page

For vendors, their dashboards will be displayed

Step 5:

Customers/Vendors can have access to any part of the system based on the button/links displayed on their home page

Placing Order by Customer:

- I. Select a vendor
- II. Navigate to the vendor's page
- III. View list of available menu items/categories
- IV. Choose an item, select the quantity
- V. Add item to cart
- VI. View Cart
- VII. Place Order

Adding/Deleting/Modifying Menu Items by Vendor:

- I. Navigate to the Menu Items page
- II. Select Add Item to add
- III. View an item on the list
- IV. Select action to modify/delete item

Updating Order Status by Vendor:

- I. Navigate to the Orders page
- II. Select an order from the list
- III. Click on action
- IV. Select and order status
- V. Update Order

4.7 Summary

Chapter 4 covered various aspects of the implementation and testing phase of the online food ordering and recommendation system. The chapter took us through various testing techniques including unit testing, integration testing, and system testing. During the implementation, challenges were encountered. The major challenge was the integration of Shadcn UI into a react.js environment. Shadcn UI by default functions with tailwind and Typescript. Fortunately, the challenge was overcome by following official documentation and expert inputs. The chapter concludes by providing a detailed guide on how to use the system to help users.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Overview

This chapter discusses insights gained during the implementation of this project. The chapter will also provide a detailed analysis of how the project's objectives were met, limitations, and challenges faced. It will conclude by offering recommendations and highlighting potential areas for future enhancements.

5.2 Objective Assessment

The main objectives of this project as stated in Chapter One are to provide an efficient food ordering platform, streamlined order management platform, personalized recommendations, and user satisfaction. Looking at the results achieved from the implementation and testing phase, the stated objectives have been achieved.

5.3 Limitations and Challenges

Developing the online food ordering and recommendation system came with several challenges that impacted the progress and timeline of the project delivery.

One major challenge encountered was integrating Tailwind CSS with ShadCN UI into the React application. This challenge took a considerable amount of time out of the project. The time that was meant to be allocated to the implementation of other tasks and features was channeled into debugging and resolving the issues in order to render the components as expected. Thus, causing a considerable amount of delay.

Additionally, the major limitation encountered during the course of this project was the lack of a proper dataset to feed our recommendation engine. The recommendation system, as we know, heavily relies on data from the customers' past order history, and the menu items available in the system's database. That comprises all the available items added by all registered vendors. At the start, there was data scarcity to feed our model as there were no registered vendors. To feed our model we heavily relied on a test dataset which in turn slightly affected the meaningfulness of the recommendations. With a real dataset, from both provided items by vendors and the customer's order history, the recommendation will be more meaningful.

5.4 Future Enhancements

In the future, this system can be enhanced and improved in several ways for better usability and user experience. Some potential areas to look at include:

Developing a mobile application: A mobile version of this system will improve the user experience as it will enable users to access the system without the need to visit a browser.

Feedback and Rating feature: Adding this feature will improve user engagement. By dropping feedback on a particular item, a customer can help other customers make informed decisions before placing an order. This feature will also put vendors on their toes and ensure that all items are of high quality and standards.

Integration of Secure Payment Options: The introduction of a secure payment option into the system can improve the overall user experience and also pave the way for the introduction of delivery services. This can be either by integrating a third-party payment service or building a wallet for the customers.

5.5 Recommendations

For the broader success of the system, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Introduction of Collaborative filtering technique to recommend items based on the other users with similar interests. As the number of users increases, collaborative filtering can help in broader recommendations, not just narrowed to a single user.
2. To provide accurate and relevant recommendations for user's, vendors should have a proper guideline for describing their menu items.
3. To further maximize profit, vendors from outside the university can be invited to register as the system is designed to accommodate many of them.

5.6 Summary

This chapter concludes the project by offering a thorough review of the system. The final system delivered has met its objectives as reviewed in section 5.2. Subsequently, section 5.3 took us through the limitations and challenges faced during the development of the system and how we approached and addressed them. In section 5.4 we look at areas that can be enhanced in the future for the continuous success of the system. Lastly, section 5.5 offered recommendations on how the system can further be used and utilized.

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